

TRANSLATION CONCEPTS IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

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Annotation. This article discusses the concepts of translation in modern linguistic research. At the moment, the translation process and mechanisms have not been fully investigated or disclosed. They represent a kind of "black box" for most scientists, decoding the records of which could help modern linguistics in the study and understanding of the mechanisms of speech and language formation, which in turn can lead to new horizons in modern research. Methodologists and psychologists consider the problem of translation skills and their formation among the most important skills for the theory and practice of translation.

Keywords: written speech, speech activity, translation process, translation, skill, translation process, text, oral speech, language, translation language.

Language is a universal system for presenting and storing knowledge in written and oral forms. Language is a means of communication. Speech is the process of communicating through language. Thanks to speech communication, the ability for speech activity is formed. Speech activity is a set of psychophysiological actions of a person aimed at the perception and understanding of speech or its reproduction in written or oral form. Shcherba L. V. identified three aspects of language phenomena and their correlation: language, speech activity and speech. These three concepts are interrelated, and this indicates the unity of language and speech. In general, speech can be divided into oral and written. Oral speech arises spontaneously in the process of natural communication and is realized through sound means. Written speech is a fixation of oral speech and is expressed by a system of graphic symbols. Written language is not learned spontaneously, and a person needs to be purposefully trained in this system. According to Vygotsky L. S., written speech is a language in representation. In order to master it, you need to recognize elements in a graphical form. Written speech does not represent the translation of oral speech into written characters, and oral speech is not the assimilation of a writing system. Written speech requires abstraction for its development. Thus, oral and written speech can be represented as two levels within the linguistic and psychological structure of speech activity. The subject of speech activity is a thought, and the means of its expression is the language system with phonetic, lexical features and grammatical means. To carry out speech activity, it is necessary to master individual speech actions. In other words, actions are units of speech activity. Speech skills are formed in the process of performing speech actions, and speech skills are formed in the process of performing a certain type of speech activity. Skills, abilities, and knowledge are formed simultaneously when performing actions. The ability of a person to practically use the language system (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, reading and writing techniques) is called language competence, and the ability to use the language appropriately and appropriately in certain situations is called speech competence. Speech skills must be brought "to an

optimal level of perfection". In order to reach the level of skills, speech action must acquire such qualities as автоматизированность automaticity, stability, flexibility, lack of focus of consciousness on the form of execution, lack of stress and rapid fatigue. That is, in the process of speech activity, the following skills are formed: speaking, reading, writing, and the ability to perceive by ear.

The ability to translate is a complex derivative of the above-mentioned skills. Nikolaeva S. Y. divides skills into the following types of skills: Productive skills-speaking and writing-are based on reproductive skills:

- grammatical skills (i.e., skills in choosing the morphological and syntactic design of an oral or written speech unit).
- lexical (skills of choosing, communicating and implementing a lexical unit in oral and written speech); pronounced speaking skills (i.e., skills of articulation and intonation);
- graphic and spelling skills of writing (skills of graphic representation of speech and spelling according to the rules of spelling).

Receptive skills-listening and reading-are based on the following receptive skills:

- grammatical (skills of recognizing grammatical and predicting syntactic structures of oral or written speech),
- lexical skills (i.e., the ability to recognize sound or graphic images of lexical units and understand them directly).
- auditory (skills of perception and recognition of sounds, sound combinations, intonation in oral speech),
- perceptual (i.e. skills of perception and recognition of letters, letter combinations, punctuation marks in written speech).

Methodologists and psychologists consider the problem of skills and their formation among the most important skills for the theory and practice of translation. The main role in language acquisition is played not by the knowledge of certain words and grammatical constructions, but by the level of development of oral and written speech skills. The formation of skills and abilities is the basis of the translation training process.

Translation is a complex multi-faceted and multidimensional type of human speech activity, which includes listening and speaking (interpretation), reading and writing (translation). So, it is natural that translation has become the object of study of not one, but many sciences. Translation is studied in literary studies, which studies the translation of fiction. The psychophysical aspect of translation, which occurs in the translator's head at the time of translation, is a subject of study in psycholinguistics. Attempts to automate translation fall within the purview of such sciences as cybernetics, information theory, and applied mathematics. The methodology of teaching foreign languages considers the practical aspect of translation in order to teach foreign languages. Translation requires reading and writing skills. Among speech reading skills, one can distinguish the ability to separate basic information in a text, the ability to predict its content, the ability to understand important information based on context, and the ability to pay attention only to material that is essential for translation, or not to pay attention to unknown language material.

It is believed that the formation of competence in reading depends on the formation of intellectual skills of the student, such as forecasting, analysis of what is read, a combination of logical and semantic activities, classification and systematization of acquired information. Educational and organizational skills play an important role. Compensatory reading skills also

play a significant role, such as using language and contextual guesses to understand what is read, ignoring unknown language material that is not important for understanding. The level of formation of speech skills affects the development of reading skills. This includes reading technique skills, lexical skills, and grammatical skills. Psychophysiological mechanisms of reading include visual perception, internal pronunciation, text segmentation, operational memory, anticipation, long-term memory, and comprehension. Psychologists distinguish several layers of understanding foreign-language texts: understanding fragments, understanding the main idea, full-fledged understanding, and critical understanding. Among the skills of writing, that is, the ability to express thoughts in writing, there are the ability to build logical texts, stylistic skills, the ability to design written texts in accordance with the type and genre, and the ability to briefly convey the idea of the original. Speech writing skills are divided into technical — graphic and spelling, and speech-lexical, grammatical and comprehension skills. Writing skills are formed on the basis of declarative knowledge (rules of spelling and syntax, linguistic and foreign studies) and procedural knowledge (extralinguistic, language and speech standards for writing texts, knowledge of how to plan, produce and correct a written statement, etc.). Writing skills have such qualities as purposefulness, productivity, independence, dynamism, etc. integration. The formation of writing skills is influenced by a number of factors:

- psychological factors.
- psycholinguistic factors;
- linguistic factors.
- sociolinguistic factors.

Foreign language speech competence in writing covers three main stages: perception, perception and reproduction, and production. At the first stage of perception, the original text is read and analyzed. In the second stage, students learn the individual actions needed to create a new text. And at the third stage, your own text is produced. The text can be in oral, written, or even thought form. The text is the goal, object, and result of translation. The text is a speech product that helps to carry out verbal communication. The text consists of utterances that the speaker creates by selecting language units and combining them with the grammatical rules of the given language in accordance with their communicative intentions. The construction and understanding of an utterance is based on both linguistic and extralinguistic factors. But a text is not just a collection of individual utterances. The text is a complex structural and meaningful whole. Its communicative potential is much greater than the aggregate content of its individual utterances. The translator must perceive such integrity of the original text and ensure the integrity of the translation text that he creates.

In a number of modern translation concepts, the translator is considered primarily as a creator of the text in the target language. The task of translation is to convey the content of the original text. Ideally, the translator should strive to recreate the entire global content of this text (this is why theoretical translation studies often point out that it is not just the original text that should be translated, but the text and context). We see that the global content consists of the expressed meaning and semantic components that the original author has in mind. The general meaning of the translation text also consists of the same elements. So, the optimal solution to the problem should be an accurate reproduction of the original language content in translation, so that translation receptors can deduce a specific contextual and implicit meaning on their own. However, this raises some difficulties. First of all, it is known

that the linguistic meaning of the original is almost never reproduced in full in translation, and it is almost impossible to achieve full compliance here. The actual similarity of the content of the original and translated texts is achieved at different levels of equivalence with the loss of individual semantic elements. Even within the same language, the linguistic meaning of a statement can vary to different degrees. When we talk about translation, we usually talk about either the process of creating the translation text (the process) or the result of such a process (the translation text). At the beginning of the development of the linguistic theory of translation, most scientists believed that the process of translation should be the main subject of research in this scientific discipline. Later, translation was considered within the broad framework of interlanguage communication, and in the field of translation studies. we combined not only the result and the translation process, but also all the communication participants and all the factors that affect the translation process and result. So far, the disclosure of the translation mechanism, the description of the translator's actions, his strategies and tactics are of considerable interest both for theory and practice. The study of the translation mechanism is complicated by the fact that it is the result of mental processes that are not available for actual observation. The researcher has to use various indirect means to see what is going on in the translator's head. It seems obvious that there are certain stages in the translation process that can occur simultaneously or follow one another.

Of course, there are two stages in translation: the stage of understanding and the stage of translation, the reproduction of the text in another language. Some of the authors suggest also highlighting the third stage of editing, this stage of final polishing of the translation. Since psychologists and linguists have long studied the processes of understanding and creating texts, translation studies can use the data of these sciences, assuming that such processes occurring in the head of a translator cannot fundamentally differ from the processes occurring in the head of other, "normal" people. And, indeed, the vast majority of translation concepts are based on our knowledge of how people understand and create texts. At the same time, research helps to separate some features of the translator's communicative behavior. As a rule, the translator should understand the text with which he works more deeply than the reader "usually" does, for whom the original language is his native language. This additional "depth" of understanding arises from the need to make final conclusions about the content of the text, as well as take into account the requirements of the translation language. The translator largely acts intuitively and often cannot explain and logically justify why he acts this way and not otherwise.

If we are talking about a translation, this means comparing the original texts and the translation. If the result of a translation is presented as it should have been in accordance with the expectations of this model, it can be argued that the model "works", although this does not at all indicate that the translator consciously used this particular model. Currently, there are several such models in translation theory. The most common of them are situational, transformational, and semantic models. The situational model considers the translation process taking into account linguistic concepts about the relationship between language and reality. The situational translation model is based on the fact that any situation can be described using any language. If the language doesn't have a name for a specific reality, you can still create new units in that language, or describe such elements by combining existing units.

To explain the mechanism of translation, you can use the provisions of psycholinguistics on the structure of speech activity. Just as in any kind of human activity, speech activity can be divided into several stages. First, there is a motive that encourages action, then there is a goal that must be achieved to satisfy the motive with the help of a speech work, then the internal program of the future utterance, the construction of the utterance in internal speech and its verbalization in oral or written speech. Translation theory pays special attention to the data of psycholinguistic studies, which indicate that the internal program of speech formation functions not on the basis of natural language, but on the individual subject-image code of a person. The problem of the translation process itself is an interesting field for research, since it lies at the intersection of many sciences, and its solution is a necessary component of modern research in the field of creating artificial intelligence and natural language processing.

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